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The main factors affecting the financial stability and efficiency of a commercial organization

KEYWORDS

financial stability,
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ABSTRACT

Introduction. The relevance of the research topic is that financial stability is the basis for long-term sustainability and development of the organization. Good economic performance significantly increases confidence in the organization and facilitates access to capital. Companies with high financial stability can effectively face competitors as they can invest in innovation, development of new products, and expansion of business operations.

The article analyzes the factors that affect a business organization’s financial stability and efficiency.

Materials and Methods. The materials of the present study were articles from periodicals. Comparative, general scientific, and factor analysis were used as research methods in the complex approach to the study of reporting data.

Results of the study. Compared to solvency assessed about current assets and long-term liabilities of the organization, financial well-being is determined based on the relationship between different types of monetary sources and compliance with their composition. The ability of the enterprise to make timely payments and finance its activities on an extended basis indicates its stable financial condition. The study of financial stability of organizations offers a broad perspective in conjunction with new technologies, social factors and changing economic conditions, making it critical to the future of business.

Conclusion. The system of fundamental indicators characterizing the financial condition of an economic entity includes the following: indicators of liquidity and solvency; indicators of financial stability; indicators of funds turnover; indicators of profitability of the enterprise; indicators of composition and dynamics of financial results; indicators of changes in the sources of equity capital; indicators of analysis and cash flow.

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INTRODUCTION

The relevance of the research topic is that financial stability is the basis for the long-term sustainability and development of the organization. In the face of economic uncertainty such as currency fluctuations or changes in interest rates, the study of financial stability helps the company identify and minimize potential risks. Notably, investors and lenders pay attention to a company's financial stability when deciding whether to invest. Good economic performance dramatically increases an organization's credibility and facilitates access to capital. Companies with high financial stability can effectively face competitors because they can invest in innovation, new product development, and expansion of business operations.

The financial stability study also identifies areas for asset management and resource mobilization improvement, which are essential for improving the organization's overall performance.

Thus, studying factors affecting financial stability is necessary to successfully manage organizations in today's environment.

The article analyzes the factors affecting a commercial organization's financial stability and efficiency.

Literature review

According to the European Central Bank, financial stability is a state in which financial institutions, markets, and market infrastructure work efficiently and resist various shocks without reducing the efficiency of converting savings into investments. Financial stability reflects the state of financial performance and the need to optimize the allocation of resources continuously. In addition, it serves as a fundamental goal of economic development [1].

According to I. G. Sahebi et al, after the 2008 financial crisis, financial stability became a critical tool used worldwide to withstand external risks and shocks which, sometimes creating a turbulent environment, can vary in intensity and frequency and can be attributed to internal or external factors of the system. Resilience is the ability to withstand more significant risks, recover quickly from risks, and reduce degradation due to specific hazards [2].

W. Gleißner et al. write that financial sustainability is underrepresented both in scientific research and in the practice of sustainability management of organizations. The authors consider financial sustainability the most critical control parameter complementing the value of shares. They can be regarded as by risk-averse investors as a secondary condition for investment decisions. The authors also suggest that a firm's financial strength should be measured in terms of four conditions: 1) firm's growth, 2) firm's ability to survive, 3) level of exposure to risk of loss, 4) profit [3].

E. Siopi and T. Poufinas study the impact of internal and external factors on the profitability and financial stability of insurance groups in the European Union. The authors show that receivables management efficiency and the state of the economy have a significant positive impact, while underwriting risk and size significantly adversely affect profitability and financial strength [4].

J. Xiang et al. investigate the determinants of UK insurance companies' financial performance based on their financial strength ratings. The authors show that profitability, liquidity, size, and organizational form significantly affect UK insurance companies' financial efficiency [5].

According to M. Sajid, financial stability is necessary for economic growth because it builds confidence and trust and promotes investment in green development. The authors investigate the relationship of institutional quality, renewable energy, green growth, environmental sustainability, and financial inclusiveness with financial stability. According to the authors, financial inclusiveness and institutional quality are positively related to financial stability, while green growth, environmental sustainability and renewable energy mechanisms are achieved through financial stability [6].

J. Kanoujiya & S. Rastogi study the impact of technical efficiency on the company's financial distress. A sample of 78 non-manufacturing companies in India was taken for analysis. According to the authors, technical efficiency affects the economic distress of the company [7].

According to E. Bayraktar, the study of the impact of business analytics as an evidence-based decision-support mechanism on organizational effectiveness remains insufficiently researched. The authors proposed a methodology of production frontier analysis for a comprehensive assessment of the main factors concerning the level of achievement in managerial, operational, and financial efficiency [8].

A. Sorgente et al. write that after the 2008 economic crisis, much research was devoted to studying predictors of financial well-being. However, still no consensus is reached on conceptualizing the notion of financial well-being. Their study aims to contribute to separating the construct of financial well-being from the construct of economic stress. The authors showed that subjective financial well-being and stress differ significantly daily [9].

Thus, investigating the causes of organizations' financial soundness and performance is a research problem. Moreover, organizations' financial sustainability results from the interaction of multiple factors, including internal and external factors. The difficulty lies in the fact that not all aspects can be quantified, which makes it difficult to build models and analyze the impact of each.

In an ever-changing economy and markets, financial sustainability factors can change rapidly. This leads to the need to update research and analysis constantly and to difficulty in forecasting. Some factors can have both positive and negative effects on financial sustainability,

depending on the context. Adapting models or approaches to different market conditions is a significant research challenge.

An in-depth analysis of factors' impact on financial sustainability requires qualitative and quantitative data, which are not always available, especially in SMEs.

Integrating research findings into practical recommendations for organizations is essential. The difficulty is that scientific findings do not always directly apply to real-life scenarios.

Thus, the scientific challenge is the need for a comprehensive and constantly updated analysis of factors affecting financial sustainability, considering their diversity and variability.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The materials of this study were articles from periodicals (International Review of Financial Analysis, Journal of Business Economics, International Advances in Economic Research, Economic Change and Restructuring, Environmental Science and Pollution Research, Information Systems Frontiers, Social Indicators Research, The Journal of Chinese Sociology, Indian Economic Review, Multimedia Tools Apple, Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science, etc.).

The research methods used were comparative, general scientific, and factor analysis in the context of a comprehensive approach to the study of reporting data. The case study method was also applied: a case study on revealing the peculiarities of assessing the financial condition of OJSC 'Confectionery firm TAKF' was studied. The main source of information on the economic activity of commercial organizations is the organization's accounting (financial) statements.

RESEARCH RESULTS

Economic analysis often involves standard methods and formulas for calculating ratios and indicators. Financial stability is based on the entire production and acts as the main link to the organization's aggregate stability.

There are four types of financial stability, which can be assessed according to the appropriate scale of risks of loss of financial stability:

1. Risk-free zone (the enterprise has absolute solvency and independence of financial position).
2. Acceptable risk zone (the enterprise has an independent financial position that guarantees solvency).

3. Critical risk zone (solvency is broken, but there is a possibility to restore the balance by replenishing the sources of own funds due to reduced accounts receivable and acceleration of inventory turnover).
4. Zone of catastrophic risk (the enterprise is entirely dependent on borrowed sources of financing) [10].

Financial stability is an integral part of the overall sustainability of the enterprise, the balance of the financial flow, and the availability of funds that provide the organization with the support it needs for a certain period, including servicing loans received and production. It determines the financial independence of the organization. Financial stability is a forecast on solvency indicators over a long period. Compared to solvency, assessed about the organization's current assets and long-term liabilities, financial well-being is determined based on the relationship between different types of financial sources and compliance with their composition. The leading indicators of the organization are shown in Table 1.

Table 1

Main results of TAKF activity in 2020-2021

Name of indicators	Unit	2021	2020	In % to the previous year
1	2	3	4	5
Production	tons	20,275	19,218	105.50%
Product sales	tons	20,319	19,255	105.53%
Proceeds from product sales	thousand RUR	2,466,772	2,042,256	120.79%
Net profit	thousand RUR	75,686	105,006	72.08%
Labor productivity per 1 worker (IPP)	tons/person	22.74	20.99	108.34%
Labor productivity per 1 worker (IPP)	thousand RUR/ person	3630.1	3007.5	120.70%

A decrease in the net profit indicator is associated with a significant price increase for the main types of raw materials used in confectionery products. The outstripping growth rate of cost of sales relative to revenue is associated with decreased purchasing activity in 2021 due to the COVID-19 pandemic. The average annual capacity of the enterprise in 2021 was 19,575 tons of products, and the personnel was 934 people, making TAKF one of the largest employers in Tambov. Economic activity of the organization leads to an increase or decrease in assets, capital, profit, and liabilities, which are reflected in the balance sheet. Therefore, first of all, let us consider the leading indicators of TAKF balance sheet and study the structure of

property and sources of its formation. The central part of the composition of current assets is accounts receivable. If at the end of 2019 the specific weight of accounts receivable was equal to 37.6%, at the end of 2021 it decreased to 34.4%. However, accounts receivable increased in absolute terms by 74,251 thousand RUR (or 13.8% of the initial value). The balance sheet shows accounts receivable minus the allowance for doubtful debts. At the beginning of 2021, the reserve amount was equal to 21,064 thousand RUR or 4.02% of short-term accounts receivable. At the end of the year, the reserve amount was equal to 22,481 thousand RUR or 3.6%. This is evidence that the company is practical in selecting customers, and the products are shipped on conditions of deferred payment.

Revenue growth in 2021 compared to 2020 amounted to more than 20%, so such accounts receivable growth is not critical for the company. The organization's cash has significantly decreased. If at the end of 2020, TAKF had 133,298 thousand RUR on its accounts, at the end of 2021 this amount decreased to 11,081 thousand RUR. As shown above, the organization's cash is placed in long-term financial investments, significantly reducing the balance sheet's liquidity. On the positive side, the enterprise is characterized by a steady retained earnings growth. In two years (2020-2021), it increased by 180,737 thousand RUR. The specific weight of capital and reserves is 63.4%, that is, the factory mainly relies on its sources of funds.

The following factors have a positive impact on financial stability: increase in the balance sheet currency by the end of the reporting period, positive dynamics of current assets exceed, positive dynamics in comparison with non-current assets, short-term and long-term liabilities, almost commensurate growth rates of accounts receivable and accounts payable. It is possible to interpret commercial activity positively in case of some excess of the organization's liabilities, particularly accounts payable over accounts receivable [11].

Accounts payable occupies the main part of short-term liabilities. The negative point is overdue debt, but it is decreasing. If at the end of 2019, the amount of overdue debt was 536,988 thousand RUR, at the end of 2021, it was only 138,258 thousand RUR. Table 2 shows how the amount of overdue accounts payable changed.

Table 2

Change in the amount of overdue accounts payable in TAKF in 2019-2021

Indicator	2019	2020	2021	Change 2021/2019
Amount of accounts payable, thousand RUR	961,258	464796	466,625	-494,633
Amount of overdue debt, thousand RUR	596,988	182,082	138,258	-458,730
Share of overdue debt in total amount	0.62	0.39	0.30	-0.32

As seen from the table, both the overdue debt and its share in the total amount of accounts payables are decreasing. Thus, the financial and economic activity of the organization leads to an increase or decrease in assets, capital, profit and liabilities, which are reflected in the balance sheet. The value of non-current assets of the enterprise is slightly less than the current assets and amounts to 47.9% of the balance sheet total. It can be argued that this ratio is typical for an enterprise that belongs to the food industry. The most significant part of the composition of non-current assets is financial investments. The revenue growth in 2021 compared to 2020 amounted to more than 20%, so such accounts receivable growth is not critical for the enterprise. The organization's cash significantly decreased – at the end of 2020, TAKF had 133,298 thousand RUR in its accounts, at the end of 2021, this was 11,081 thousand RUR.

The economic literature accumulated experience diagnosing a commercial enterprise's solvency. The studies by O.G. Kovalenko, A.A. Kurilova, B.A. Shogenov present the coefficients of current solvency assessment which show the ratio of liabilities and mobile assets [12; 13].

Coefficients have significant shortcomings in assessing solvency. Domestic methods of diagnosing crisis states are based on the analysis of enterprise liquidity, which includes the analysis of balance sheet liquidity and the dynamics of liquidity ratios. These coefficients are shown in Table 3.

Table 3

Coefficients characterizing the liquidity of TAKF in 2020-2021

Indicator	Normative value	2021	2020	2019
Current liquidity ratio	1.5-2.5	1.71	1.73	0.80
Quick liquidity ratio	0.7-1.5	1.24	1.34	0.60
Absolute liquidity ratio	> 0.2	0.03	0.28	0.01
Total liquidity ratio of the company's balance sheet	≥ 1.0	0.72	0.84	0.37
Equity ratio	≥ 0.1	0.22	0.23	-0.26
Functional capital maneuverability ratio		0.66	0.54	-1.05

As seen from the table, all the ratios corresponded to the normative value only in 2020. In 2021, the absolute liquidity ratio decreased from 0.28 to 0.03. However, as practice shows, such value for the absolute liquidity ratio is acceptable; most industrial enterprises successfully settle their obligations, and the value considered normative is overestimated. The net profit of the enterprise in 2021 was less than the same indicator for 2020, which was 29,320 thousand

RUR or 27.9%. These negative changes affected the value of profitability indicators. Return on assets decreased by 2.1 percentage points, return on equity decreased by 3.5 percentage points, and return on sales (on profit from sales) decreased by 4.0 percentage points. All this indicates that the efficiency of using the enterprise funds is decreasing, and if this trend continues, TAKF may face problems in the future.

The ability of the enterprise to make timely payments and finance its activity on an extended basis testifies to its stable financial condition. The key characteristic of the organization's financial condition is its solvency, which means the ability of the organization to pay all its obligations. The financial condition of the enterprise from a short-term perspective is assessed by liquidity and solvency indicators, which characterize the ability of the enterprise to make timely settlements on short-term obligations to counterparties.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Prospects for studying the organization's financial stability can be distinguished in several directions. With the advent of new technologies such as artificial intelligence and big data, study of economic stability can use more advanced methods of analysis [14; 15] which will allow more accurate risk prediction and identification of patterns in financial performance.

More and more organizations understand the importance of sustainability and social responsibility. The results of financial stability research can be integrated into ESG concepts (environmental, social and corporate factors) [16; 17], which will allow organizations to consider economic and non-financial risks.

With globalization and dynamic changes in international markets, financial stability research will help companies adapt to new economic realities such as the pandemic, supply chain changes, and consumer behavior [18; 19].

With new regulations and standards in the financial sector [20; 21], especially in response to the global economic crises, further research on financial stability will be essential to understand their impact on organizational structure and financial reporting.

Study of financial stability practices will become particularly relevant in crises such as economic recessions, allowing organizations to develop recovery and adaptation strategies.

Thus, studying organizational financial stability offers a wide range of perspectives in conjunction with new technologies, social factors, and changing economic conditions, making it critical to the future of business.

CONCLUSION

Financial stability is an integral part of the overall sustainability of the enterprise, balance of monetary flow, availability of funds that provide the organization with the support it needs for a certain period, including the servicing of loans received and production. The decisive part of the increase in production at the enterprise can be obtained from the existing fixed assets and production facilities, which is several times greater than the annual introduction of new assets and facilities. Financial stability is formed in the business process and is the main component of the stability of the enterprise. Economic conditions can generally be stable, unstable, and in crisis. A stable state is achieved if the business entity can finance its activities and pay its obligations on time. In addition, sustainability is also characterized by the ability of a person to be solvent in case of adverse economic conditions. If a company or enterprise cannot perform these actions, its state is characterized as pre-crisis, i.e., unstable.

The system of fundamental indicators characterizing the financial condition of an economic entity includes the following: indicators of liquidity and solvency; indicators of financial stability; indicators of turnover of funds; indicators of profitability of the enterprise's activities; indicators of the composition and dynamics of financial results; indicators of changes in the sources of equity capital; indicators of analysis and cash flow. It is necessary to forecast the economic condition to determine the organization's prospective financial condition and measures to achieve it. In general, the cash flow forecast is an essential component of this forecasting. The reliability, accuracy, and validity of the methods used guarantees the effectiveness of the forecasting system.

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